

DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION OF ECG BY USING BAYESIAN REGULARIZATION NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Automatic Detection and classification of Cardiac abnormalities and Arrhythmias from a limited number of ECG signals is of considerable importance in critical care or operating room patient monitoring. We propose a method to accurately classify the heartbeat of ECG signals through the Neural Networks. Feature sets are based on QRS complex of the ECG signal. It is difficult to detect P and T wave due to the overlaps and variations in amplitudes of other signals. In this paper we propose a method for Automatic Detection and classification of the P, QRS and T wave. Bayesian regularization neural network is used to learn the characteristics of P, QRS and T wave, which provides high detection rate of 94.6% for P, 96.7 for R and 91.6% for T.

Keywords: ECG, Kaiser Window, Bayesian Regularization, Levenberg- Marquardt, QRS Complex

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INTRODUCTION

A standard scalar electrocardiogram consists of P - wave, PR - interval, PR - segment, QRS - complex, ST - segment, ST interval and T - wave. The P - wave represents atrial depolarization, the QRS complex left ventricular depolarization and the T - wave left ventricular repolarisation [1].

To precisely measure the time between two electrical events in the ECG, it is necessary to identify parts of the waveform. The real-time detection of the P and T wave is challenging due to its relatively low amplitude, low signal to noise ratio, and the presence of the other adjacent waves. Previous works in P wave detection usually rely on digital signal processing techniques [2] even Many of these approaches delineate either P or T - waves of ECG waveforms, whereas a few approaches delineate both P and T - waves.

Murthy & Niranjana used discrete Fourier transform (DFT) to delineate P and T waves, while Murthy and Prasad used discrete cosine transform (DCT). Thakor and Zhu used adaptive filters for delineation of P - waves. Pietka used a combination of syntactic methods and methods based on measurement vectors by applying the attribute grammars. Trahanias and Skordalakis used attribute grammar for the detection of P and T - waves [3]. In this article, we made use of the processed dataset from the standard CSE database. Since the ANN has the advantage of automatic feature extraction from within the signal [17], in this only conducts simple filtering on the signal, which can improve the network's generalization and decrease signal distortion. In addition, there were some missing data which we processed it by utilizing MATLAB software interpolation function. Finally, the processed ECG data are employed directly as input to the ANN model.

For detection of P- wave and T-waves: For the detection of P and T-waves should be capable of appreciating the low slope and low magnitude of the wave components, as contrasted to QRS-complexes containing peaky waves with prominent slope and magnitude.

Further, to ensure sufficient magnitude of the extracted feature, so as to meet the thresholding needs; the proposed algorithm is to detect the components of P and T wave. The detection of P- and T-waves is done with the reference of QRS on and off time, in that it search intervals for P and T - waves between each successive pair of QRS off time and the subsequent QRS-on time[5].

ECG Dataset Pre-processing

Preprocessing of raw ECG signals is necessary to reduce noises such as power-line interference, baseline drift, and high-frequency noises caused by muscle contractions and electrode movements, which can interfere with fiducial point detection and heartbeat classification and make a substantial contribution to the overall classification outcome. In a clinical setting, the collected ECG signals are typically combined with various interferences [14]. To extract the useable signal, the original data must be de-noised in order for the classification to be more precise. In the field of ECG denoising, low-pass filters, band pass filters, and wavelet transform are commonly utilized [15, 16].

ECG Classification

Many authors have utilized various types of neural networks to classify ECG data. In this study, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are employed for the classification. ANNs are self-adaptive, data-driven, non-linear, accurate, fast, scalable, and robust to noise [18]. The advantages of ANN are as follows: (1) it enables a non-linear mapping between inputs and outputs utilizing activation functions such as sigmoid to handle non-linear problems such as ECG signal classification. (2) It can produce outcomes that are comparable to or better than statistical or deterministic techniques. (3) ANN can simulate the lower frequencies of the ECG, which are fundamentally non-linear, adaptively. (4) ANN reduces the ECG signal's time-varying and nonlinear noise features [19].

METHODOLOGY

Neural networks have been trained to perform complex functions in various fields like pattern recognition, identification, classification, speech and extras. In that once the network weights and biases are initialized, the network is ready for training with proper network inputs p and target outputs t . In automated bayesian regularization, it is desirable to determine the optimal regularization parameters in an automated fashion. In this approach overcome the over-fitting problems with early stopping and Bayesian Regularization.

Early stop approach is the process in which the data set is divided into three subsets: training, test, and verification sets. The test set is used to test the trend of the prediction accuracy of the model trained at some stages of the training process. At much later stages of training process, the prediction accuracy of the model may start to get worse for the test set. This is the stage when the model should cease to be trained to overcome the over-fitting problem [6,7]. The Bayesian Regularization approach involves modifying the usually used objective function, such as the mean sum of squared network errors (MSE or E_d)

$$F = E_d = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (e_i)^2$$

$$F = \beta E_d + \alpha E_w$$

Where: α and β are parameters which are to be optimized in Bayesian framework of MacKay [8,9]. It is assumed that the weights and biases of the network are random variables following Gaussian distributions and the parameters are related to the unknown variances associated with these distributions. It is a known fact that the optimal regularization technique requires quite costly computation of the Hessian matrix. To overcome this drawback, Gauss-Newton approximation to the Hessian matrix is used. The process of bayesian framework is the use of bayesian regularization function is a combination with Levenberg- Marquardt training process. Standard back propagation is a gradient descent algorithm in which the network weights are moved along the negative of the gradient of the performance function. The trainbr algorithm generally works best when the network inputs and targets are scaled so that they fall approximately in the range [-1, 1]. If the inputs and targets do not fall in this range, we can use the function map min max to perform the scaling. In this the input layer consisted of nodes and in the subsequent hidden layer process neurons with the standard sigmoid activation function are used [10].

Algorithm for Detection

1. Load ECG database files case by case as shown in fig (a)
2. Implement FIR band pass filter with Kaiser Window for removing of noise as shown in fig (b).
3. The output of the above step is passed through the neural network, which is having P as an input.
4. The training function is to train neural network with bayesian regularization function having target T with a defined learning rate $\mu=0.05$ and number of epoch=4. Further, in this step mapminmax function is used.
5. Then the output of mapminmax is trained and simulated with the input. After simulation we get the stable and desired output.
6. We apply the threshold condition to detect and mark the R-wave as shown in fig (c).
7. Now between two consecutive R-peak time intervals we will find the P wave by applying threshold condition i.e. 10% of R wave as shown in fig (d)
8. Now between two consecutive R-peak time intervals we will find the T wave by applying threshold condition i.e. 30% of R wave as shown in fig (e)

Graphical Results of P, QRS and T – waves

Figure a,b : CSE - ECG database case no 004 V1 (a) Input, (b) filtered output

Figure c,d e: CSE - ECG database case no 004 V1 (a) Input, (b) filtered output

Testing Results

In this paper bayesian regularization neural network is used to learn the characteristics of QRS complex to detect P and T wave on the standard CSE database. Bayesian regularization gives accurate and best results. The table shows the actual number of QRS complexes (R peaks), number of P and T wave detected, true positive (TP), false negative (FN), and false positive (FP) detection for entire CSEECG library dataset-3. Each ECG record of the dataset is of 10 sec duration sampled at 500 samples per second, thus giving 5000 samples. The table also shows the detection rate (*DR*), positive predictivity (+P) and sensitivity (*Se*).

Accuracy

Accuracy is a data measurement that accurately determines correctness [14]. It is the ratio of the sum of True Positives (TP) and True Negatives (TN) to a total number of data inputs provided. The confusion matrix for signal recognition is required for accuracy computation. The accuracy is calculated mathematically as follows:

$$\text{Accuracy} = (TP + TN)/(TN + FN + TP + TN) \quad (1)$$

Sensitivity

Sensitivity is the sum of all positives recognized as positive by the algorithm [14]. It is the ability of a network to recognize signals belonging to the same class. It is the proportion of True Positives (TP) to the total of True Positives (TP) and False Negatives (FN). It's also referred to as detection probability, recall, and true positive rate. The confusion matrix for signal categorization is required for specificity calculation. Sensitivity is calculated mathematically as follows:

$$\text{Sensitivity} = TP/(TP + FN) \quad (2)$$

Table.1 Overall results of QRS wave detection for the entire CSE data base

Actual no. of QRS	True Positive TP	False Negative FN	False Positive FP	Detection Error Rate DR %	Positive Predictivity +P %	Sensitivity Se %
17988	17705	283	37	1.7	98.64	98.6

Table.2 Overall results of P wave detection for the entire CSE data base

Actual no. of P	True Positive TP	False Negative FN	False Positive FP	Detection Error Rate DR %	Positive Predictivity +P %	Sensitivity Se %
16301	15410	891	40	5.7	94.86	94.6

Table.3 Combine overall results of T wave detection for the entire CSE data base

Actual no. of T	True Positive TP	False Negative FN	False Positive FP	Detection Error Rate DR %	Positive Predictivity +P %	Sensitivity Se %
17061	15618	1443	927	13.8	92.0	91.6

CONCLUSION

The algorithm developed in MATLAB is implemented, with ANN based on Bayesian regularization function, for detection of P and T wave. The algorithm is rigorously tested on entire CSE-ECG dataset-3, which includes an accurate range of morphologies and vast variety of cases. The resultant values are shown in Table 1, 2 with significantly low values of FP and FN and excellent values of DR, +P and Se.

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